

Local extrema of apparent brightness of Uranus and Neptune seen from their moons

Harald Schröer
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An observer stays in a space ship that circles round a moon.

Explanations: mag= stellar magnitude, °=deg, '=angular minute, ''=angular second
AE = astronomical unit = 149598500 km , h=hour

Uranus seen from Miranda:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Miranda - Uranus [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 18h - 19h	-11.72	7	0.000868	31.31-31.33 increasing	22.70 R=73.92
2.1.2017 11h - 13h	-16.01	92-93 decreasing	0.000870	148.48 - 148.57 decreasing	22.65 R=73.82

Uranus seen from Ariel:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Ariel – Uranus [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 13h - 15h	-11.28	9	0.001273	35.41 – 35.42 increasing	15.43 R=54.32
2.1.2017 19h - 22h	-15.14	91	0.001275	144.55-144.60 decreasing	15.40 R=54.26

Uranus seen from Umbriel:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Umbriel - Uranus [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
2.1.2017 19h - 21h	-10.53	9-10 increasing	0.001783	35.20-35.22 increasing	11.00 R=40.24
4.1.2017 21h - 24h	-14.43	90-91 decreasing	0.001769 - 0.001770 decreasing	144.72 - 144.86 decreasing	11.08 R=40.52

Uranus seen from Titania:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Titania-Uranus [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
5.1.2017 0h - 4h	-9.48	9	0.002912 -0.002919 decreasing	35.38-35.39 decreasing	6.71-6.73 R=25.27 -25.29 increasing
9.1.2017 7h - 14h	-13.34	91	0.002920	144.48 - 144.53 decreasing	6.71 R=25.22

Uranus seen from Oberon:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Oberon-Uranus [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
5.1.2017 1h - 4h	-8.83	9	0.003901	35.21-35.22 decreasing	5.02 R=19.01
11.1.2017 16h - 24h	-12.71	91	0.003905	144.64-144.65 decreasing	5.01 R=18.99

Neptune seen from Naiad:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Naiad-Neptune [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 4h - 9h	-11.65	4	0.000323	22.85 – 22.89 increasing	61.66 R=105
1.1.2017 8h - 9h	-17.02	96	0.000323	156.56-156.79 decreasing	61.66 R=105

Neptune seen from Thalassa:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Thalassa - Neptune [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 4h - 9h	-16.92	95	0.000335	154.08-154.21 increasing	59.23 R=103
1.1.2017 8h - 9h	-11.93	5	0.000335	25.58-25.62 increasing	59.23 R=103

Neptune seen from Despina:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Despina - Neptune [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 4h - 5h	-16.81	94-95 decreasing	0.000351 - 0.000352 decreasing	153.23-153.67 decreasing	56.10-56.28 R=100 - 101 increasing
1.1.2017 8h - 9h	-11.84	4-5 increasing	0.000352	25.69-25.77 increasing	56.10 R=100

Neptune seen from Galatea:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Galatea - Neptune [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 1h - 2h	-11.49	5	0.000414	25.73 -25.77 increasing	47.14 R=91
1.1.2017 6h - 8h	-16.45	95	0.000414 - 0.000415 increasing	153.31 - 153.34 increasing	47.02-47.14 R=90-91 decreasing

Neptune seen from Larissa:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Larissa - Neptune [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 3h - 4h	-11.10	5	0.000491	25.57 – 25.71 decreasing	39.41 R=81
1.1.2017 10h - 11h	-16.08	94-95 increasing	0.000492 - 0.000493 increasing	153.88-154.11 increasing	39.24-39.32 R=80 - 81 decreasing

Neptune seen from Proteus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Proteus - Neptune [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 6h - 7h	-15.06	94 – 95 increasing	0.000786 - 0.000788 increasing	153.24-153.77 increasing	24.25-24.32 R=56 - 57 decreasing
1.1.2017 19h - 21h	-10.15	5	0.000785 - 0.000786 decreasing	26.12-26.17 decreasing	24.32-24.35 R=56 - 57 increasing

Neptune seen from Triton:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Triton-Neptune [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
2.1.-3.1. 2017	-12.52	87-89 decreasing	0.002370 - 0.002378 decreasing	138.91-139.58 decreasing	7.98-8.01 R=20 - 21 increasing
5.1.2017 20h - 23h	-9.06	11	0.002372 - 0.002379 decreasing	39.45-39.47 decreasing	7.97-8.00 R=20 - 21 increasing

Neptune seen from Nereid:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Nereid - Neptune [AE]	Angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
24.2.-25.2. 2017	-9.13	80-87 decreasing	0.010520 - 0.011201 decreasing	127.78 - 137.52 decreasing	1.69-1.80 R=4.3 - 4.6 increasing
13.3.2017 21h - 24h	weaker than +2.00	<1	0.015281 - 0.015329 increasing	2.47 – 2.49 increasing	1.23-1.24 R=3.1 - 3.2 decreasing

Made with Stellarium and Planetarium.